

CICM-2023
26-28 July 2023, MIST, Dhaka

Review of National Building Code Design Provisions, Retrofit and Safety Guidelines for Nuclear Power Plant (NPP) Zone in Bangladesh

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Abstract. The Bangladesh National Building Code (BNBC) is a pivotal document that provides guidelines for safe and efficient construction in Bangladesh. However, with the growing need for energy, nuclear power plants (NPP) are becoming increasingly prevalent in the country. Therefore, there is a need for specific design provisions, safety guidelines, and retrofit measures for buildings located in the NPP zone to ensure their safety and security. This paper presents a comprehensive review and analysis of the BNBC's design provisions, safety guidelines, and retrofit measures for buildings in the NPP zone. The study identifies the strengths and weaknesses of the current BNBC provisions and proposes recommendations for improvement. The review of the design provisions covers various aspects, especially seismic design. Similarly, the safety guidelines cover various topics such as emergency planning, radiation protection, and security measures. The retrofit guidelines consider both the structural and non-structural retrofitting of existing buildings to ensure their safety in the unexpected event of an NPP accident. The study finds that the current BNBC provisions provide a good foundation for building design and safety but they do not adequately address the unique challenges of buildings in NPP zone. The study recommends that specific provisions be developed for buildings in the NPP zone, including more stringent requirements for structural seismic design, safety, and emergency planning. The study also recommends the development of more detailed retrofit guidelines for existing buildings in the NPP zone. Overall, the study highlights the importance of ensuring the safety and security of buildings in the NPP zone in Bangladesh and provides valuable insights into the design provisions, safety guidelines, and retrofit measures required for achieving this goal.

Keywords: Bangladesh national building code (BNBC), nuclear power plant (NPP), seismic design, safety guidelines, retrofit guidelines.

1 Introduction

Starting from Chalk River, Canada, in 1952 to yet about more than two dozen of nuclear power plant accidents occurred namely Three Mile Island (United States, 1979), Chernobyl (Ukraine, 1986), Fukushima Daiichi (Japan, 2011) accidents the majors [1]. When a nuclear power plant experiences a significant explosion or accident, the devastation on nearby buildings can be severe. The operational area of the Rooppur NPP encompasses a considerable space [2], including the reactor buildings, turbine halls, cooling systems, fuel storage facilities, and administrative and support buildings. The plant adheres to rigorous safety standards and protocols to ensure the protection of workers, the environment, and the public but the locality exists within only one kilometer shown from the present satellite view (see Fig. 1).

(Source: Google Maps, 24.067184561659243, 89.04561106644209)

Fig. 1. Partial operational area and radius of the locality from the nuclear reactor.

It is important to acknowledge that no technology is entirely risk-free. Ongoing monitoring, continuous training, and regular safety assessments are crucial to maintaining a high level of safety. In case of an unexpected nuclear explosion, the force of a nuclear explosion can cause immediate destruction to nearby buildings. The blast wave generated by the explosion can shatter windows, collapse walls, and even level entire structures. The closer a building is to the epicenter of the explosion, the more severe the damage is likely to be due to the induced seismic wave [3]. Nuclear power plant explosions can lead to fires that can quickly spread to surrounding buildings. The intense heat generated by the explosion can ignite flammable materials within the vicinity, resulting in widespread fires that can engulf nearby structures. The flames can cause further damage and make firefighting efforts challenging. One of the most significant concerns associated with a nuclear power plant explosion is the release of radiation. Depending on the severity of the incident, radioactive materials can be released into the environment, posing serious health risks to those exposed. Buildings near the explosion may become contaminated, and prolonged radiation exposure can have long-term effects on human health. In the aftermath of a nuclear power plant explosion, nearby buildings may need to be evacuated to ensure the safety of the residents. Contaminated

structures can pose health risks to those who enter, and decontamination efforts may be required before people can return. The process of decontamination can be time-consuming, complex, and costly. The devastation of buildings near a nuclear power plant explosion can extend beyond the immediate vicinity. The release of radioactive materials into the environment can contaminate soil, water sources, and the surrounding ecosystem. This contamination can have long-lasting effects on plants, animals, and the overall environment. The potential devastation of nearby buildings in the event of a nuclear power plant explosion can vary depending on several factors, such as the magnitude of the explosion, safety measures in place, and emergency response efforts. Although nuclear power plants have extensive safety protocols and multiple layers of protection to prevent accidents. In the unexpected event of an NPP explosion incident, building code predefined safety provisions and protocols for newly constructed buildings and retrofit guidelines for existing buildings can minimize the damage to surrounding areas. The BNBC does not specifically address safety provisions [4], and NPP explosion-induced seismic design for buildings in the vicinity of nuclear power plants. Developing safety guidelines to include in BNBC specific to nuclear power plants and their surrounding areas that are developed and enforced by the appropriate regulatory bodies can assure emergency preparedness, evacuation plans, and protective measures to minimize the potential impact of an incident at a nuclear power plant to save a numerous life.

2 Theory and Analysis

2.1 Impact of NPP Blast Energy and Structural Damage

The intensity and extent of seismic waves generated by a nuclear power plant explosion or accident can depend on various factors, including the magnitude of the explosion, the depth and location of the event, and the geological characteristics of the area. Seismic waves can travel long distances, affecting structures and the surrounding environment. Monitoring and studying seismic waves generated by nuclear power plant explosions or accidents are crucial for assessing the extent of the event and understanding the potential impacts on structures, infrastructure, and the safety of nearby communities. In such an unexpected NPP explosion incident, a big portion of blast energy gets converted to seismic shock waves and the energy can be converted to earthquake (EQ) magnitude through Eq. (1) developed by Gutenberg and Richter [5].

$$\log E = 11.3 + 1.8 M \quad (1)$$

Where E indicates the blast energy in ergs and M is the magnitude of the wave. From the analysis with Eq. (1) for Chornobyl Disaster [6] as a reference of nuclear blast energy, it is estimated that 5.7 magnitude EQ can be happened due to a nuclear explosion.

Equation (2) developed by Davenport [7], is used to estimate the spectral (Z) peak ground acceleration (PGA) within a 35-kilometer radius from the explosion center since

International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) guideline shows 30-kilometer radius is a critical safety zone for NPP [8] and the estimated Z values are shown in Table 1.

$$Z = 279 \times 10^{-6} e^{(1.8M)} / R_e^{1.64} \quad (2)$$

Here, Z is the spectral PGA, M is EQ magnitude and R_e indicates the epicentral distance of the building from the origin of the NPP explosion center.

Table 1. The series of spectral PGA-Z values for a radius of 35 kilometers.

R_e - Epicentral Distance (km)	Spectral PGA (in g) - Z value
5	1.45
10	0.72
15	0.48
20	0.36
25	0.29
30	0.24
34	0.21
35	0.20

The above data analysis comprehends a range of ground acceleration of 1.45g to 0.24g when the epicentral distance is between 5km to 30km where BNBC has a range of maximum ground acceleration consideration is 0.36g [4], specifically in Rooppur (Seismic Zone-2) the maximum spectral acceleration is taken as 0.2g ($Z=0.2$).

2.2 Analysis of Existing Retrofit Guidelines

The method of seismic evaluation of existing buildings is related to Eq. (3) which shows the inequality between the seismic demand and seismic capacity [9].

$$C \times F \geq (2/3) Z \times I \times C_t \quad (3)$$

Where C is the strength index, F indicates the ductility factor, Z is the seismic zone coefficient, I indicates the structural impotence factor and C_t demonstrates the normalized building response spectrum. The right portion of the inequality equation describes the seismic demand and here the Z is taken as similar to as specified in BNBC. The existing buildings within the critical safety area of Rooppur NPP are under the threat of structural damage and radiation exposure. The retrofit guideline including existing building seismic evaluation and visual rating methods [10,11] published in 2022 does not consider the NPP zone and also does not recommend any nuclear radiation protective material for further retrofit.

3 Nuclear Radiation Safety Analysis

In the event of a nuclear power plant explosion or accident that results in the release of radiation, it is crucial to have protection measures in place for local buildings and their occupants. However, the Bangladesh National Building Code (BNBC) does not currently provide any guidelines or recommendations regarding radiation-protective building materials or measures to protect lives inside buildings from radiation hazards.

3.1 Use of Nuclear Radiation Protective Material

Nuclear radiation protective construction materials and systems are designed to minimize the penetration of radiation into buildings and provide shielding to occupants [12]. The commonly used protective materials and building systems:

- **Lead Shielding:** Lead is a dense and effective material for radiation shielding. It is commonly used in the construction of walls, doors, and barriers in areas where radiation protection is required. Lead-lined walls or lead bricks are often incorporated into the design to create a barrier that absorbs and blocks radiation.
- **Concrete:** Concrete is another material that provides significant shielding against radiation. High-density concrete, which contains heavy aggregates such as barite or magnetite, is often used in the construction of radiation-protected areas. The thickness of the concrete walls can be designed to meet specific radiation shielding requirements.
- **Steel and Metal Alloys:** Certain metals, such as steel and specific metal alloys, possess good radiation attenuation properties. These materials can be used in the construction of structural components, shielding doors, and barriers to reduce radiation exposure.
- **Borated Polyethylene:** Borated polyethylene is a composite material that contains boron, which has excellent neutron shielding properties. It is commonly used in nuclear facilities to shield against neutron radiation. Borated polyethylene sheets or blocks can be incorporated into building structures or installed as modular shielding panels.
- **Radiation-Resistant Glass:** Special types of glass can be used in windows, doors, and observation areas to provide visibility while reducing radiation transmission. These glasses are typically laminated with multiple layers of radiation-attenuating materials, such as lead or bismuth, to provide effective shielding.
- **Ventilation and Air Filtration Systems:** Effective ventilation and air filtration systems are important in nuclear facilities to control airborne radioactive particles. These systems are designed to prevent the entry of contaminated air into protected areas and ensure the circulation of filtered and clean air.
- **Sealing and Containment:** Ensuring airtight seals and containment structures is essential to prevent the leakage of radioactive materials. Proper sealing of penetrations, joints, and connections can minimize the potential for radioactive particle infiltration.

- **Monitoring Systems:** Radiation monitoring systems, including detectors and dosimeters, can be integrated into building systems to continuously monitor radiation levels. These systems provide real-time information on radiation levels and help in assessing the effectiveness of protective measures.

The design and implementation of nuclear radiation protective construction materials and systems require careful planning, engineering expertise, and adherence to regulatory guidelines. Each facility may have specific requirements based on the type and intensity of radiation involved. Therefore, consulting with radiation protection experts and regulatory authorities is essential to ensure the appropriate design and implementation of protective measures.

3.2 Individual Safety Measures

In the unlikely event of a nuclear power plant explosion or any other significant incident, individuals in the affected locality must take appropriate safety measures. While the specific measures may vary depending on the circumstances and guidance provided by local authorities, here are some general safety measures that individuals should consider [13]. The general protection measures that can help mitigate radiation exposure:

- **Sheltering:** Buildings can provide a certain level of shielding against radiation. Staying indoors and taking shelter within a building can help reduce exposure to external radiation. It is important to close and seal windows, doors, and other openings to prevent the entry of radioactive particles.
- **Distance:** Increasing the distance between individuals and the source of radiation is an effective way to reduce exposure. If a nuclear power plant accident occurs, following evacuation orders and moving to a safe distance from the affected area is crucial.
- **Time:** Minimizing the time spent in areas with high radiation levels can reduce overall exposure. Prompt evacuation, relocation, and adherence to safety instructions from authorities are essential in minimizing the time spent in potentially hazardous areas.
- **Personal Protective Equipment (PPE):** In situations where radiation exposure is imminent or unavoidable, appropriate PPE can be used to reduce direct contact with radioactive materials. This may include items such as gloves, masks, and protective clothing that are specifically designed to shield against radiation.
- **Monitoring and Early Warning Systems:** Implementing radiation monitoring systems can help detect and measure radiation levels in the environment. Early warning systems can provide timely alerts and instructions to building occupants, enabling them to take necessary protective measures.
- **Decontamination:** If individuals come into contact with radioactive materials, proper decontamination procedures should be followed. This may involve removing contaminated clothing, showering, and disposing of contaminated materials in designated containers.
- **Communication and Education:** Providing clear and accurate information to building occupants about the situation, risks, and protective measures is essential. Regular communication channels, such as public announcements,

emergency broadcasts, and digital platforms, can help disseminate information effectively.

- **Coordination with Emergency Response Authorities:** Building management should establish effective communication and coordination with local emergency response authorities. This ensures a timely response, access to accurate information, and appropriate guidance on protective measures for radiation exposure.

It is important to note that specific protection measures and guidelines may vary depending on the nature and severity of the radiation release. Local regulations, emergency response plans, and guidance from radiation protection agencies should be followed for the most appropriate and up-to-date information regarding protection from radiation exposure.

4 Discussions

Apart from design provisions and retrofit guidelines, safety measures encompass various aspects such as emergency preparedness, evacuation plans, and communication protocols. This discussion should evaluate the effectiveness of the safety measures outlined in the National Building Code for the NPP zone, including the coordination between building occupants, emergency response agencies, and the nuclear power plant operators. It should also address the integration of advanced technologies, such as early warning systems, radiation monitoring, and communication networks, to enhance the overall safety and response capabilities. In reviewing the National Building Code provisions for the NPP zone, it is essential to consider the alignment with relevant international standards and guidelines. Comparing the provisions with internationally accepted best practices, such as those recommended by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) and other nuclear regulatory authorities, can help identify any discrepancies and areas where the code may need to be updated to meet higher safety standards. An effective safety framework goes beyond the code itself and involves raising public awareness and providing appropriate training. This discussion should examine the measures in place to educate building owners, occupants, and emergency responders about the specific safety requirements and protocols within the NPP zone. It should also explore avenues for continuous training and information dissemination to ensure a well-prepared and informed community.

5 Summary

A thorough review of the National Building Code provisions, retrofit guidelines, and safety measures for the NPP zone in Bangladesh is crucial to identify strengths, weaknesses, and areas for improvement. By addressing any gaps and incorporating lessons learned from global best practices, the code can be updated to ensure the highest level of safety and protection for buildings and occupants within the vicinity of nuclear power plants. Close collaboration between regulatory authorities, experts, and stakeholders will be essential to enhance the resilience and preparedness of buildings in the NPP zone in Bangladesh. Additional suggestions for conducting large-scale research projects involving experimental and finite element modeling (FEM) on nuclear

explosions and their effects on surrounding structures, specifically considering soil-structure interaction (SSI) in the event of a nuclear reactor explosion at a specified depth.

References

- [1] J. P. V. Dorselaere, A. Thierry, and M. C. Jean. "Research on severe accidents in nuclear power plants." *Nucl. Power-Oper. Saf. Environ., InTech* (2011): 155e182.
- [2] S. Saha, K. Roy, S. Roy, M. A. Rahman and M. Z. Hasan. "Rooppur nuclear power plant: current status & feasibility." *Strojnícky časopis-Journal of Mechanical Engineering* 68, no. 3 (2018): 167-182.
- [3] P. N. S. O'brien. "Seismic energy from explosions." *Geophysical Journal International* 3, no. 1 (1960): 29-44.
- [4] HBRI. "Bangladesh National Building Code (BNBC)." Housing and Building Research Institute, Bangladesh (2020)
- [5] M. Båth. "The relation between magnitude and energy of earthquakes." *Eos, Transactions American Geophysical Union* 36, no. 5 (1955): 861-865.
- [6] Pakhomov, Sergey A., and Yuri V. Dubasov. "Estimation of explosion energy yield at Chernobyl NPP accident." *Pure and applied geophysics* 167 (2010): 575-580.
- [7] P. Davenport. "Neural network analysis of seismic intensity from instrumental records." In *Proceedings of the 13th world conference on earthquake engineering*, paper, no. 692. (2004)
- [8] IAEA. "Commissioning Guidelines for Nuclear Power Plants." IAEA Nuclear Energy Series No. NP-T-2.10, IAEA, Vienna (2018)
- [9] HBRI. "Technical Guidelines for Seismic Evaluation of Existing Reinforced Concrete Buildings in Bangladesh for Extended Application of PWD Seismic Evaluation Manual." Housing and Building Research Institute, Bangladesh (2022)
- [10] S. M. M. Islam, M. A. R. Bhuiyan, and T. U. Mohammed. "A Proposal of Visual Rating (VR) Method for Seismic Vulnerability Assessment of Existing Unreinforced Masonry Buildings." 6th ICACE Proceedings (2022). Volume: 840-847p. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7472151>
- [11] M. S. Islam, H. Alwashali, D. Sen and M. Maeda. "A proposal of Visual Rating method to set the priority of detailed evaluation for masonry infilled RC building." *Bulletin of Earthquake Engineering* 18 (2020): 1613-1634.
- [12] T. Furuta and T. Fumiaki. "Study of radiation dose reduction of buildings of different sizes and materials." *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology* 52, no. 6 (2015): 897-904.
- [13] T. Ohba, T. Koichi and L. Liudmila. "Evacuation after a nuclear accident: Critical reviews of past nuclear accidents and proposal for future planning." *Environment International* 148 (2021): 106379.